

PEER- REVIEWED INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL

***Aarhat Multidisciplinary
International Education Research
Journal (AMIERJ)
ISSN 2278-5655***

Impact Factor :0.948

Bi-Monthly

VOL - II

ISSUES - V

[2013-14]

**Chief-
Editor:**

**U b a l e
A m o l
B a b a n**

[Editorial/Head Office: 108, Gokuldharm Society, Dr.Ambedkar chowk, Near TV Towar,Badlapur, MS

REVITALIZING PROFESSIONALISM AMONG TEACHER EDUCATORS FOR KNOWLEDGE SOCIETY

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Introduction

A profession is a paid occupation specially one that involves prolonged training and a formal qualification.

According to Macmillan dictionary, “a profession is a job that you need special skills and qualifications to do, especially one with high social status.”

The above two definitions of professionalism focuses on three dimensions

The above three dimensions are very well fit in the profession of teacher educators. As being a teacher educator means a lot of hard work and higher qualification like M.Phil,PhD,JRF/NET. It takes a lot of time to gain all these higher degrees. Secondly all this

results in handsome payment in universities and thirdly it also results in a good social identity and status. Though, once there was a time when being a teacher was supposed to be the plum in the society. Teacher educators were hardly identified because of lack of teacher training institutions or type of education system. But now the scene has changed because of privatization of education system and mushroom growth of teacher institutions and researches in this field has given this field its due importance.

WHO IS A TEACHER EDUCATOR? One who ‘teaches the teacher’ is a teacher educator. A teacher who teaches in the classroom is a product of those skilful hands we call ‘teacher educators. A teacher educator is that human being who prepares the humans for strengthening the pillars of a nation. A teacher is the reflection of his/her teacher educator. Like students mimic their teachers in the classroom, student teachers also learn what their teachers teach them. A nation’s future builds in the classrooms therefore job of a teacher becomes very crucial. A teacher is like a doctor and scientist who creates and generates the future minds and skills to run the knowledge and economy of a nation. The job of teacher educator thus focuses on producing such fraternity for the schools who can deal with a variety of professions which develops in the mind of school students. It is the duty of teacher educators prepares the student teachers to nurture and flourish the young minds for a progressive country. Now the job of teacher educators is like of preparing a doctor and scientist, who have to teach their student about all the required equipments and chemical reactions that can happen. For this, teacher educators themselves need to have the knowledge and skill of all that is required in the classrooms. Teacher education profession is facing new challenges day by day. A lot of knowledge, skill, value, cognition etc. is required for being a teacher educator. John wooden has also said “I think

the teaching profession contributes more to the future of our society than any other single profession”.

WHAT IT MEANS TO BE A PROFESSIONAL for a teacher educator?

- **Passion And Intelligence**

Teacher educators should have the passion and praise for their profession and Passion for the teaching, Passion for delving in the deep studies, in spite of following the already beaten path teacher educators should always be ready to variety problems and to find the solutions. This can be done by self ego involvement in the profession. Teacher educator should not choose the job only for the sake of being paid but they carry a certain type of respectability and praise for their profession. Intelligence in a profession means how smartly one keeps oneself updated and smart in the field. T.E. should also keep them abreast with every kind of knowledge and updated.

- **Accountability**

Teacher educators are accountable to the pupil teachers, management they are working in, society and nation at large. As the teachers who teaches in the class room performs as they

have been taught by their teachers. If they are or are not able to satisfy their pupils it will put a question mark on the knowledge of the teacher educators. Teacher educators are the keys of channelizing social changes also. As they are themselves the sources of knowledge as well creators of more knowledge sources. This is a kind of chain reaction that happens in the society. This change ultimately affects the nation.

- **Mastery**

Mastery over the subject matter means teacher educators should not only have the knowledge of their teaching subjects only but also they should be very well equipped with all the sources of knowledge and information. Like they should have the knowledge of ICT. It should be made mandatory for all the teacher educators to undergo in service or pre service training of using information technology in their teaching. They should be provided with training time to time to refreshing their knowledge. They should also learn to master a mindful, calm response to an emergency.

- **Awareness Towards Self And Others**

Awareness is about overreaching knowledge about the self, others and surroundings. Teacher educators must delve deep in the several areas like emotions, behaviours, preferences locus of control, personality type, social competence and the like. Self awareness puts us in the position to know where we are strong and where we are weak. What we need to retain and what we need to eliminate. Awareness towards others and surrounding includes the awareness of the others expectations and all that goes in the teaching society in special and overall society in general.

WHAT IS KNOWLEDGE SOCIETY? KNOWLEDGE IS POWER. It is not a new concept. All societies have been knowledge societies but their models were different earlier societies were class based with no or little intellectual communication. But with the advancement of new technology and economy Communication has developed globally. The targets in every sphere of societies are knowledgeable and productive mass. UNESCO ha defined knowledge societies as “knowledge society should be able to integrate all its members and to promote new forms of solidarity involving both present and future generations. Nobody is excluded from knowledge societies, where knowledge is public good, available to each and every individual.”

Thus knowledge society is a mindset of a large group which works collectively toward the strengthening of productivity.

FEATURES OF A KNOWLEDGE SOCIETY CAN BE CHARACTERISED

EDUCATION FOR KNOWLEDGE SOCIETY READY MEMBERS REQUIRES

end product: knowledge society ready members

PROFFESIONALISM AMONG TEACHER EDUCATORS IN KNOWLEDGE SOCIETY

Change at the part of duties and functions of teacher educators are required. Following are the major changes that are required

In the new age of technology and education demands of classrooms have changed. Demands from the teachers have also changed. The problem in this scenario is that the most conservative elements are being forced to take cognizance of the changes occurring all around them. Now when the world has been won over the technology use in the classrooms at teacher training institutions also need to be upgraded. The training program of teacher training institutions should focus on

Conclusion

Hence at last I would like to conclude with one message to the teaching fraternity that get up and get ready for teaching emotional technosavy members of the society so that their skills can be upgraded for the maximum utilization in productivity. Productivity here I mean the result of all the thoughts and skills of learners that ultimately result in the creation and up gradation of the society.

It is required to provide proper infrastructure and opportunity to the teachers to be productive. Need of the hour is to reassessing the quality concern of the educational institutes where teachers are prepared for the future classes. It is the time to think for some IIEs in India like IITs and IIMs. Because without quality enhancement goal of developing a knowledge society will not be achieved